

Pedagogical attachments and Virtual Reality: on immersion with digital technology in school

Toon Tierens ^c
and Samira Alirezabegi ^d

^aCentre for School Improvement, Zurich University of Teacher Education, Zurich, Switzerland; ^bMethodology of Educational Sciences Research Group, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium; ^cFaculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Helmut Schmidt University, Hamburg, Germany; ^dLaboratory for Education and Society, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

ABSTRACT

This paper explores what comes to matter pedagogically when introducing Virtual Reality (VR) in Vocational Education and Training (VET) schools. In spite of the general understanding that digital technologies rarely work as anticipated, research exploring how VR unfolds in schools and how it gives way to specific pedagogical forms of acting, thinking, and relating to others, is scarcer. Addressing this gap, we explicate our ethnographic fieldwork in one Belgian school through sensitivities derived from Science and Technology Studies (STS). Specifically, thinking with the concept of ‘attachment’ (and its corollary ‘detachment’) to indicate how educational ways of being are continuously in the making in classroom practices, our fieldwork shows how different types of attachments (i.e. *communizing, instancing, modulating, conditioning*), that emerge through concrete and heterogeneous acts, relate to different forms of ‘immersion’. Conclusively, the paper discusses the need to further unpack how technologies always come to matter pedagogically in specific ways and argues that an appropriate terminology is necessary to articulate this. To this extent, we propose the concepts of ‘pedagogical attachments’ and immersion to enunciate the pedagogical specificity of what is at stake when introducing digital technologies in the classroom.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 6 February 2025
Accepted 30 September 2025

KEYWORDS

Virtual Reality; attachment; immersion; Vocational Education and Training; ethnography; Science and Technology Studies; school education

1. The turn to virtual reality in education

Over the past decades, Virtual Reality (VR) technology that offers varying degrees of perceptual immersion has evolved from a popular science fiction narrative (e.g. Clarke’s ‘The City and the Stars’, 1956) and an impractical technology (e.g. Sutherland’s ‘Sword of Damocles’, 1968), into a commercial technology increasingly experimented with across societal sectors (Harley, 2024). While VR can be broadly defined as any ‘virtual’ environment (Chalmers, 2022), its recent popularization has largely focused on VR’s digital adaptation in the form of a personal Head-Mounted Display (HMD; henceforth

CONTACT Toon Tierens Centre for School Improvement, Lagerstrasse 2, Zurich, 8090, Switzerland

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group.

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

'headset').¹ Frequently heralded as innovative and pioneering, VR is promised to revolutionize the field of education by replacing traditional educational methods through 'full immersion' and by offering endless possibilities for educational innovation (Spilski et al., 2019; Stender et al., 2021). While critical concerns regarding the widespread use of VR have been raised (e.g. psychological impact of VR on children; Madary & Metzinger, 2016), these are largely sidelined by VR-enthusiasts in reference to the benefits VR would bring for educational quality (Rose, 2018).

In general, promises of VR are most prominently celebrated in the context of Vocational Education and Training (VET), where the overall didactic focus lies on teaching students vocations alongside general courses, often through hands-on practice. To address persistent challenges VET schools face in facilitating students' transition to future workplaces (Jossberger et al., 2015), there has been a growing emphasis on leveraging digital technologies to simulate workplace scenarios within the classroom environment (Dahalan et al., 2024; Enochsson et al., 2020). Despite these efforts, digital technologies are often perceived by teachers and students as suboptimal substitutes for 'real' hands-on experiences (Carlsson & Willermark, 2023). In this context, VR is celebrated as a transformative innovation, supposedly enabling 'immersive' hands-on practices in realistic, open-ended workplace scenarios and safe interaction with virtual objects and characters, without real-world constraints – where immersion is understood as perceptually embedding an individual in an open-ended virtual environment via headsets (Jongbloed et al., 2024; Simeone et al., 2022). Often employed as a promotional rhetoric by the technology industry, such VR immersion is said to automatically lead to better student engagement (Lucia et al., 2024). Consequently, VR is posited as a pivotal innovation for VET that could provide interactive engagements that facilitate smoother transitions from school to the workplace (Lege & Bonner, 2020). However, VR is not unequivocally celebrated as a positive force. Within the growing research on VR in education, concerns are being raised as well, particularly regarding temporal, practical, and economic constraints of VR in relation to the everyday realities of schooling (Paulsen et al., 2024). Most notably, it has been noted how VR requires a vast amount of work by teachers (e.g. learning how to use VR, integrating it into curricula), which is counter to the rhetoric of VR developers that often ignores institutional and organizational preconditions of schools (Fransson et al., 2020).

Notwithstanding the importance of the existing field of VR research, and the emergent concerns related to VR in everyday schooling, the approach it takes still appears to be largely symptomatic of a wider discourse that instrumentalizes the way technology 'improves' education, offering a solutionist perspective. Such an instrumentalist and solutionist attitude separates affordances of technology from the broader educational environment in which technology becomes integrated and assumes further technological developments are an inherently positive force in solving educational issues, smoothing out potential discrepancies (Bayne, 2015; Williamson, 2018). Conversely, critical empirical research that explores the day-to-day situatedness of digital technologies has indicated that, generally, when they are introduced in school practices, both significantly more and significantly less happens than initially expected from simplistic technology-user narratives (Hangartner et al., 2024; Mörtzell, 2024). Rather than serving merely as instrumental solutions to – or causes of – specific educational issues, as is often assumed in the idealization or

criticism of technologies, research indicates that technologies seldom achieve their intended outcomes and expectations (e.g. how innovative, tech-driven reforms unexpectedly re-emphasize traditional educational structures and disciplinary measures) (Sims, 2017). In other words, an expanding field of critical research emphasizes that digital technologies are, in a general sense, differentially enacted in messy ways and variously maintained in educational practice (Bacalja, 2024; González López & Büchner, 2024). Equally emergent in this work, though still less apparent, is how this differential enactment of technology matters pedagogically. Here, pedagogy does not refer to didactics per se, but to how technology affects how particular matters become vital for schooling and contributes to the formation of relations between people and (curricular) objects of concern. This is specifically the case for VR, as educational research has yet to explore how these existing insights relate to VR technology in (VET) schools (though for the local configurations required for VR to fit educational settings see Forsler, 2024; for VR and creative design in elementary schools see; Mills & Brown, 2022). There is, thus, still a notable gap in critical educational research related to understanding how VR is enacted in educational practice and, ultimately, showing how these enactments come to matter pedagogically.

In this paper, we aim to avoid both an instrumentalist approach and a general claim that technology is differentially enacted. Rather, we foreground VR as a case to explore what matters pedagogically in technological enactments in school education. To do this, we draw on a three-month ethnography in a VET school in Flanders (Belgium). In Flanders, the Ministry of Education and Training has recently made substantial investments to promote the adoption of VR in schools (Flemish Government, 2024). The case of Flanders can hereby be understood as an example of a broader European interest in VR, claiming it is 'the' technology of the future for VET to increase educational quality (e.g. European Commission, 2023; Flemish Government, 2019). Conceptually, we draw on insights from Science and Technology Studies (STS) to ethnographically explore VR and the *attachments*, and *detachments*, that emerge through concrete acts and that give shape to forms of (technological) immersion. The concept of attachment allows to enunciate the continuous making of educational relations and highlights what and who comes to matter in schooling (Cone, 2024; Decuyper & Simons, 2019; Hennion, 2017). By drawing on the concept of attachment, immersion is conceptualized not as an inherent quality of VR technology but as an outcome of sociomaterial attachments in the classroom. In this sense, immersion is a specific mode of engagement with technology and other actors, indicative of particular patterns of thinking and acting in schools (de Vasconcelos, 2021; Latour, 1999). While immersion can then be understood in a general sense (i.e. in relation to digital technology in schools as such), VR is highly unique in its design and thus exemplary to further explore forms of (digital) immersion in the classroom. Our analysis of the fieldwork, which will be presented through vignettes, shows how specific attachments (*communizing, instancing, modulating, conditioning*), emerging through concrete acts, give shape to different forms of immersion (*as objectual togetherness, as displacement*). Conclusively, the article underscores the importance to make explicit how different technologies matter pedagogically in specific ways in schools. To articulate this, it is crucial to develop a tailored educational vocabulary that highlights the pedagogical nuances of technologies in school education. To this end, we propose that 'pedagogical attachments', and the forms of immersion they give rise to, are one way of

systematically articulating how technology becomes distinctively entangled with pedagogical practice in schools.

2. STS and attachments

Generally, in STS, technology is not considered as an object with inherent properties but as a social practice that continuously takes shape, while itself giving form to social practices (Latour, 1992). Technology, therefore, is understood as both being enacted through its relations with other phenomena in practice, and simultaneously as equally always enacting educational realities itself (Sørensen, 2007). This indicates, for instance, that the presumed ‘virtuality’ of VR is always tethered to the non-virtual, material, and tangible (including seemingly banal materialities, architecture, and other people) (Suchman, 2016). The perceived bifurcation between ‘the virtual’ (i.e. digital occurrences) and ‘the real’ (i.e. occurrences ‘outside’ the digital) is thus entangled, manifesting in different ways (Woolgar, 2002). Hence, the digital is seen as simply a part of the fabric of everyday life (Macgilchrist, 2021) – an idea similarly developed through the concept of the ‘postdigital’ (Jandrić et al., 2023). An STS lens guides us to closely trace how such entanglements precisely unfold and how technologies mobilize, and are mobilized in, day-to-day educational practice (Adams & Thompson, 2011). In this sense, STS does not function as a theory that explains phenomena, but as offering sensitivities that direct researchers’ attention and perception to practices (Mol, 2010). Specifically, it explores the ways technologies affect patterns of (educational) activities and contribute to the fore- and backgrounding of elements in practices, and thus form who/what becomes important and who/what consequently recedes into obscurity (Law, 1993).

Given this general STS lens, VR technology manifests the entanglement between the digital and the analogue in specific ways by foregrounding certain spatial, sensory, and relational configurations (Davidsen & Paulsen, 2024). To tease out the pedagogical specificities of VR, we focus explicitly on the concept of *attachment*, and conversely *detachment*, as a way to attend to the coming together and mutual (re-)shaping of people and technologies, and how as a result (educational) practices and worlds take form (de Laet et al., 2021). Attachment expresses the emergent relations between people and objects throughout their acts, where some relations come to matter more than others for educational practice (Aberton, 2012; cf. Latour, 2005b). Conversely, detachment indicates how attachments come and go, and how the attachments that are important for a practice continuously need to be made (Candea, 2010). In this sense, one is always attached, always made to act and accord with ways of relating to others, with attachments continuously being (re-)negotiated in practice (Hennion, 2017). Attachments are thus generative insofar as they hold people and objects together in specific ways (Latour, 1999), and, consequently, make particular forms of educational activity possible, whilst constraining others (cf. Gomart & Hennion, 1999). Because of this, attachments allude to something different than the general concept of relation (Hennion, 2017). Whereas relation indicates any type of heterogeneous connection between actors, attachment signifies those relations that indicate a *passionate intensification* of something and are affective in bringing into being what and who becomes of primary pedagogical concern in educational practice (Gomart & Hennion, 1999; cf.; Cone, 2024). Thus, as proposed by de Laet et al. (2021), attachment is something to ‘think with’, and allows to carefully

attend to how, in mundane practices, some socio-technical connections stick and become of concern. Hence, attachment allows telling stories of how ‘bodies, subjects, tastes, objects, communities and appreciations are produced, and come to matter, together’ (Ibid., p. 812). In this sense, attachments are those relations upheld in practice through acts of people and objects that momentarily sustain and hold together the very possibility of educational practice, while simultaneously always being in the making (Decuyper & Simons, 2019).

By drawing on this understanding of attachments, immersion marks above all an intensified way of being sociomaterially engaged in a practice and hence comes into being through attachments (Freitag et al., 2020). Or, more precisely, immersion comes to signify a mode of being affected by attachments between people and objects and of affecting others; hence, of giving way to certain forms of being in and of relating to the world, in relation to technology (Mühlhoff & Schütz, 2019). As such, attachments offer a way to articulate immersion not as something purely technological, but as something that relates to *how things come to matter pedagogically*. Immersion, then, given shape by attachments, allows to make new (conceptual) distinctions when thinking with attachments and to further open up the educational world-making capacity of technology (cf. de Laet et al., 2021).

3. Methodological complexities in studying VR

Ethnographic fieldwork was conducted from March to June 2024 in a Belgian VET school (‘Athena’²) that started to utilize VR headsets.³ Initially, fieldwork primarily consisted of participatory classroom observations in the courses of ‘Warehouse Logistics’, ‘Carpentry’, ‘Religion’, ‘Care and Well-being’, and ‘Upbringing and Nursing’, during which fieldnotes were written. Fieldwork focused on consistent and repetitive acts of people and objects that, in turn, are indicative of the unfolding of attachments. While this fieldwork adhered to the importance of ‘being there’ as a way of telling stories of everyday acts through fieldnotes (Taussig, 2011), (physically) being there simultaneously proved to be a way of not being ‘there’ in the context of VR; that is, of being partly detached from that which is unfolding. VR apps are engaged with by individuals wearing a headset, and what goes on ‘inside’ is not by default visible to an observer in the setting of a classroom (Brighenti, 2007; Pink et al., 2022). Particular elements disappeared from the stage when conducting ethnographic fieldwork in schools (e.g. data generated while using VR apps), and some elements were only visible for certain people (e.g. those wearing a VR headset). Hence, the ethnographic gaze was not given, but simultaneously in- and excluded, negotiated and practiced, and importantly, technologically configured, in the field (Garforth, 2012). This selective and partial ability to attend to VR in school practices through fieldwork, necessitated what Lury and Wakeford (2012) call methodological inventiveness; that is, not the invention of new methods per se, but the acknowledgement of the situational applicability and careful (re-) consideration of methods as to be able to attend to the research problem in specific ways.

Consequently, after the initial weeks of fieldwork, walkthroughs were conducted of all the applications teachers planned on using. This was done to more carefully attend to how attachments are generated in practices with VR. Walkthroughs imply a direct engagement with an app to understand its general design logic, the norms it installs, and the various ways the app wants a ‘good’ user to act (Light et al., 2018). In these

walkthroughs, the first author used a VR headset to systematically go through apps as an everyday user to understand their flow and desired user conduct and hence to gain an understanding of how these apps each aim to foster forms of acting and, consequently, attachment. This was done whilst simultaneously making screenshots in alternation with taking off the headset to make written memos. Furthermore, informal conversations were held with students and teachers after classes to immediately reflect on their experiences with and ideas about VR in school. By gaining insight into what apps expect of users and by reflecting with students and teachers on their experiences, we aimed to grasp what happened on VR apps (visible only to the ‘user’) in close relation to the generation of attachments through what occurred in the classroom. Additionally, at the end of the series of classes with VR, teachers and the first author organized discussion groups with students to collectively think about how things came to matter for them through VR and how they experienced constraints and possibilities. Similarly, a focus group discussion was conducted with all teachers involved at the end of the project to discuss their insight into how VR made things im-/possible in their class. Vignettes were written by drawing on the variety of empirical material, as a way of analytically rewriting how attachments unfold in practices (Bloom-Christen & Grunow, 2022). Additionally, a sketch (Figure 2) was created portraying a typical classroom scenario where VR is practiced and the attachments that consequently unfold. In what follows, these vignettes, formatted as indented text, and the sketch will be presented. Discussion will unfold throughout the vignettes as to intertwine data and analysis (St. Pierre, 2013).

4. ‘Where are you now?’ – communizing and instancing

Before a two-hour class on elderly care in the ‘Care and Well-being’ course, students gather outside their classroom, which is furnished with movable sofas, chairs, and tables, arranged to ensure visibility of the whiteboard and projector in front of the classroom. When the teacher, Carmen, arrives carrying two heavy boxes of VR headsets, one student, Roha, exclaims in frustration that she has spent all morning on her hair and that the headset will ruin it. Another student, Noreen, complains that the headsets made her nauseous during their last class. Carmen smiles and instructs the students to nonetheless ‘prepare the classroom’ for a VR lesson. All students start to rearrange the furniture to create as much open space as possible, leaving only a table at the front where they sit to listen to Carmen’s instructions. Carmen distributes bundles of papers containing exercises that require both a VR application and the course’s digital textbook. After instructing one student to remove her headphones to facilitate collective discussion, Carmen goes over the assignment with her students in detail, specifying which sections should be highlighted and outlining how to complete the tasks. Essentially, students need to use VR to explore an elderly woman’s house, of whom a description was provided on paper, to identify household tasks that need to be done (see Figure 1).

Prior to using the VR headsets, the students quietly work through the first pages of the assignment, which outlines the elderly woman’s personal situation. The room falls silent, filled only with the sound of pens and markers as Carmen sits at her desk, intermittently checking her emails and regularly walking around to look over students’ shoulders to see how they are doing. The silence is broken when a student, Mona, asks if the dog mentioned in the house description will appear in VR, adding that she would scream if it did. Once students finish the preliminary task on paper, they each pick up a VR headset and spread out around the room to find enough space for their VR work.

Figure 1. Screenshot of the virtual tour of a house. Green arrows can be clicked on to progress into another room; black disks offer hints about potential household tasks to be completed. Screenshot taken from a publicly available VR module on the Flemish platform ‘KlasCement’ (Tanghe, 2023).

Here, the shared classroom space gradually transforms to accommodate multiple individual practice spaces (see [Figure 2](#)), where various material elements of the classroom are recomposed.

While students begin exploring the virtual environment, Carmen moves between students, offering guidance by explaining aloud how to resolve issues, listening to audio from the VR headsets (e.g. voices of in-game characters) to identify where students are struggling, or by directly resolving the issue herself by taking over a headset. Despite the many indications in the paper bundle of the assignment to work individually, once students have started using a VR headset to explore the house, they spontaneously discuss their observations aloud: ‘WTF! I am in her bedroom! Mona, there’s that dog! You have to clean its “business”’. Students continue to converse and collaborate with each other by speaking while each wearing headsets in alternation with putting down the headsets to write the information they have gathered in their paper bundle, or by splitting these tasks.

While VR generally ‘screens off’ and renders invisible each other’s individual experience, students and the teacher reconfigure such ‘screening off’ by engaging with each other in diverse ways. Students remain engaged with the explorations of the elderly woman’s house because they are able to converse with one another and emphasize things that are of shared relevance for them (e.g. the dog). They thus sustain attachments with each other and VR at the same time, in relation to concrete acts of each other and the teacher (Freitag et al., 2020). For students, VR does not substitute modes of interaction (or make them obsolete). Rather, as students become variously attached through the practice of VR in the classroom, intricate ways of seeking communality with each other are perpetuated (cf. Woolgar, 2002) – that is, *communizing* attachments emerge, in the sense that engagement with a task is made of common concern by interacting with technology and, at the same time, with each other. As such, students continue interacting both in spoken as well as unspoken ways, which fosters a form of collective experience. This allows them to collaborate without direct visual contact – seeing alone, together (i.e.

seeing the same ‘thing’, a collective activity, which is done while being visually closed off from one another) (cf. Turkle, 2017). Such collective experience is sustained by students and Carmen herself in order to foster a sense of communality or shared engagement with a task.

While students continue interacting throughout the assignment, Carmen circulates around the classroom to watch what students are doing, occasionally reminding them of the exercises they need to make and urging them to explore the virtual environment fully. ‘Think. You see a toilet, what do you definitely have to do? If you’ve missed something, try again and search for all the clues’. Carmen asks her students at several moments, based on their spontaneous reactions: ‘Where are you now?’. She then puts on her own VR headset and navigates to the part of the virtual environment in which the student is at that point, talking with them about what can be seen. As Carmen later mentions, because of this she is able to partly overcome the absence of a screen, at very particular moments in time, where both she and a student can momentarily gather. According to her, this is different when students individually work on paper or on a computer in her classes, which makes it possible for her to look over students’ shoulders to see what they are doing on the screen.

While students interact both with the virtual environment and with each other, Carmen continuously attempts to create points of alignment between divergent engagements in the classroom in order to sustain communal attachments and, as a result, to make VR work relatively smoothly in the context of her classroom (cf. Law & Singleton, 2000). The efforts described here not only allow VR to function (Forsler, 2024), but also give form to attachments that bring VR into being in particular ways. Carmen’s efforts in her class primarily relate to how she is not able to look over students’ shoulders to see what they are doing, and thus she aims to find alternative ways of communal engagement with students. Significantly, Carmen synchronizes her gaze with that of a student by wearing her own headset while discussing with the student what they both see at a very particular moment in time, such as a toilet and various tasks that have to be done here, generating a (fragmented) form of shared attention and presence to a specific matter at hand. While such engagement enacts a certain communality, Carmen’s engagement with students using a VR headset is also indicative of attachments of *instancing*; that is, concrete moments where one particular moment, one instance of the engagement with VR technology, is called into being as the object of shared engagement and gathering for teacher and students. Carmen and her students continually identify precisely ‘where’ the other is located in relation to such communal object of practice. This, in turn, generates a sense of affinity and proximity despite the student and teacher being screened off from anything they can gather in front of.

In this vignette, two forms of attachments emerge, that of communizing and that of instancing, each alluding to specific ways of relating between teacher, students, and VR. Both of these attachments allude to the phenomenon of gathering, which is generated either through conversing with each other based on what one observes in VR, or through purposefully finding ways of collective engagement through something that momentarily becomes of concern for both the teacher and a student. Both forms of attachments are made possible, and sustained, through continuous interfacing acts of Carmen, her students, and moments in the VR module. Interfacing here refers to spontaneous acts (e.g. identifying where others are, discussing one’s observations, warning others about what not to do) that generate a place and time in the classroom related to a concrete matter that is put in-

between students and teacher. Through these acts, a particular ‘thing’ becomes of concern. ‘Thing’ refers here, in the sense of Latour (2005a), to a concrete something, in this case an instance of the VR module, that brings together or gathers actors with a shared commitment and generates an educational space and time of practice. Through interfacing acts, then, Carmen and her students create moments of connection, in relation to a specific object of practice, that allows them to establish communality in the physical classroom through screens, making possible attachments of communizing and instancing. By accordingly fostering interaction with one another and the thing of concern, both individual and collective ‘immersion’ in the classroom practice intensify and are made possible through one another. Immersion, then, does not (only) occur as an individual phenomenon. It rather firstly emerges relationally and communally; that is, immersion emerges as *a form of objectual togetherness*, between students, teachers, and the communal object, or thing, of practice that is engaged with both with and without VR.

Figure 2. Sketch of a typical classroom, observed during the fieldwork, with a screen (i.e. a smartboard; white rectangle, black sides), a table where students can gather, and the subdivision of the physical classroom into different virtual practice spaces (white spaces with black, dotted boundaries). These virtual spaces are shown as permeable due to technical malfunctions and interruptions by the teachers or peers. In these virtual practice spaces, students (black circles) direct their gaze inward (indicated by the arrow pointing toward the student), while simultaneously seeking outward connection with others (shown by curved arrows linking students and their virtual practice spaces), permeating the individuality of one’s engagement with VR. The teacher (grey circle, black boundary, with outward-pointing arrows) both mitigates interruptions as well as deliberately permeates boundaries.

5. ‘Watch your language! you’re still at school’ – modulating and conditioning

Nancy, who teaches courses on nursing techniques for students in the final years of secondary school, hurriedly prepares for a lesson. She appears stressed as she organizes the classroom and sets up VR headsets. Today’s lesson, part of the ‘Upbringing and Nursing’ course, focuses on teaching first aid techniques through VR. Nancy mentions: ‘There’s so much to take into account, and if I am honest, I tested some stuff again on my own yesterday and a lot went wrong’. This marks her first time using VR in an educational setting, and she knows her

students are equally unfamiliar with VR and fears it will be experienced as mostly playful. Once the students arrive, Nancy explains the lesson's goals. She instructs the students to pair up, with one student per pair putting on a VR headset. 'Create your individual space, one person per pair slowly puts on the headset, and then push this button (pointing to the "on" button), tighten the strap around your head, and start. Your partner makes sure you do not bump into anyone and that you are constantly safe and mindful of your environment'.

Students start to engage with the virtual environment, which some experience as a shock. As one student, Jocelyn, exclaims: 'Wow, I'm talking to a paramedic about a big flesh wound, which looks disgusting. He is freaking me out!' (see [Figure 3](#)). While Nancy reassures her that this equally overwhelmed her at first, another student jokingly touches Jocelyn, startling her and causing her to remove her headset in panic. 'Don't do that! I already forgot there were other people in the room as well', causing immediate engagement with the virtual environment to be momentarily interrupted. This prompts other students to do the same intermittently, but despite these distractions, most quickly return to engage with the virtual environment guided by their partner so that their activity goes on uninterrupted. Students are progressing through VR tasks whilst laughing and making comments about what they see in the virtual environment, often ignoring instructions given by their partner or Nancy herself. At one point, Jeffrey exclaims that the wound he is taking care of is too disgusting to look at, and he performs the movements to take something out of the first aid kit whilst calling for an ambulance without really paying attention. After reaching for the kit and taking out a sterile compress, Jeffrey accidentally throws it away. In trying to retrieve it, and ignoring the warning of his partner, he bumps into the classroom's wall. Frustrated, he tries again, also crouching in an attempt to get physically closer to the virtual object he is missing, but eventually he has to start over as it is not feasible for him to get the item back. Jeffrey claims he was taking care of the patient so well, only to be interrupted by some technical issues. Elsewhere, pairs of students are engaging with similar VR tasks, however following each other's commands to ensure such small accidents do not happen, regularly shouting 'Stop!', 'Careful!' or 'Back up!' to warn those wearing headsets, or even sometimes shouting 'Wait a second!' and moving furniture so the one wearing a headset can continue without being bothered.

Figure 3. Screenshot of a VR module on first aid. Screenshot taken from the website of OneBonsai, the company that has developed the VR app on first aid training used in the school (OneBonsai, 2024).

Students are engaged with the sequence of VR modules throughout the lesson, supported by their partner securing their physical safety in the classroom, and thus also occasionally interrupted by their partner who safeguards the limits of what can be done in the contours of the classroom. Students are intermittently drawn out of and pulled into their engagement with VR, either by something in the virtual environment (e.g. the voice of the paramedic) or by something in the physical classroom (e.g. VR engagement being delayed by one's partner). In this sense, students are very briefly detached from immediate engagement with VR at regular points in time by their partner. This is not done to break engagement, but rather to make it possible and to allow it to go on without being interrupted by actions that might force a student to stop engagement abruptly and completely. These brief and partial detachments, made possible by fellow students, enable those wearing VR headsets to remain engaged with VR modules and thus make possible ongoing attachments both with actors in the classroom as well as within the VR module (cf. Hennion, 2017). In other words, students' direct activity with the actors in the virtual environment, where it is needed to follow the necessary protocols to provide first aid, is made possible by their fellow students in the classroom who sustain attachments with the person using VR by warning them about where they can or cannot move in the classroom. These attachments between students delay and alter ways of practicing with VR in the classroom, for example by pausing movements to move furniture like desks or by commanding someone to back up to avoid hitting a wall. What emerges here are attachments of *modulating* that, paradoxically, enforce brief detachments with actors in the virtual environment; that is, by modulating what students can do and by bringing into being constraints for students using VR, they are limited in what they can do in the virtual environment but are enabled to continue VR engagement without complete interruption (which happens when, for example, someone hits a wall or trips over furniture).

These modulating attachments operate both as constraint and resource and can hence be understood as a generative or 'generous constraint' (Gomart, 2002, p. 521); that is, they show how practices with technology can be performed insofar as constraints are put in place and conditions are delineated. Such constraints are consistently enacted and equally, although differently, come into being through actions of Nancy.

Throughout Nancy's class, she intervenes in students' activities to make sure they are properly dealing with the tasks they have been assigned, and that VR is not used too frivolously. She occasionally intervenes in students' activities because, as she later explains, she does not think it is meaningful. At one point during Nancy's lesson, Vincent, who after a certain time of being active with one of the first aid modules, shouts: 'Fuck me! That must suck', as he refers to a wound 'his' patient has. In response, Nancy immediately shouts back: 'Guys! Watch your language! You are in a virtual world, but you are still at school', making Vincent aware again of his position as a student.

Here, Vincent's immediate engagement is briefly interrupted by Nancy. She does not do this to necessarily completely break the student's engagement, but to make it unfold differently. Vincent's engagement, like that of other students, is constrained and made to unfold in another way, which also considers how students should behave in school and not only in the virtual environment.

Nancy continuously rushes from student to student to redirect their engagement. As she later mentions, she wants them to engage with VR in pedagogically meaningful ways. Additionally, and based on her prior experience with the VR modules, Nancy regularly tells her students to ignore specific parts and to focus on aspects that the modules under-emphasize according to her, including environmental awareness when resuscitating someone.

Nancy's interruptions primarily operate as the setting of educational terms and conditions of engagement. In doing so, she similarly does not set out to break students' engagements but attempts to enable particular ways of being with VR, while discontinuing other ways. Rather than pure VR engagement becoming the primary goal of Nancy's lesson, it becomes clear that engagement with VR can unfold only in ways that comply with her own pedagogical desires (e.g. paying attention to aspects she finds more important) and the school's rules (e.g. not cursing). In this sense, attachments of *conditioning* emerge through the interplay of the virtual environment, students' engagement, Nancy's interruptions, and this in relation to the broader school environment. This implies that actors in VR aim to foster forms of engagement that are redirected through Nancy's interruptions. As such, she constrains how VR activity can unfold in the classroom and under which educational conditions this is possible (see [Figure 2](#)).

In this vignette, two other attachments emerge, those of modulating and conditioning, both alluding to how constraints for students' action in the classroom are generated through acts of other students, teachers, and VR. Throughout Nancy's lesson, unintentional and intentional actions intervene in students' interaction with VR, either to ensure students can remain engaged (e.g. avoiding bumping into objects in the classroom) or to ensure they are engaged differently (e.g. reminding students that they are still at school and that specific attitudes matter there). The emphasis of Nancy that students 'are still at school', for example, exemplifies how while VR affects what is possible within a classroom, VR is itself contingent upon emergent educational elements (such as rules, material space, expectations, and more) that delineate what it is and can be within the school (Bacalja, 2024; Woolgar, 2002). These emergent attachments, effectuating how educational practice with VR looks like, are most significantly made possible through acts of suspending, which alludes to acts that set formative limits to what engagement with VR means and how it can unfold. Such acts include warning or stopping fellow students and pointing them towards relevant things in the virtual environment. Ultimately, the attachments of modulating and conditioning bring into being immersion as *a form of displacement*. In other words, immersion is enabled by the ongoing shifting or temporary suspensions – that is, displacements – of students' primary focus between the virtual environment and the requirements of the classroom and the school. This constant movement means that immersion is not a fixed state but rather an oscillation between different modes of engagement, continuously shaped by these attachments.

6. Towards pedagogical attachments

The vignettes discussed above underscore that the way VR is expected to be integrated as an individually immersive and hands-on practice is significantly altered in the classroom. While VR affects educational practices, it becomes deeply enmeshed within the habituality and materiality of the school, partly stripping it from its ordinary use. In other words, the

school, as a particular educational environment, is both affected by VR but also significantly shifts what VR is and can do. This mutual interplay indicates the messiness and glitches that are inherent to technological enactments in educational practice (Macgilchrist, 2025). Our vignettes specifically illustrate how technology enactment in schools occurs through explicit suspensions of particular technological affordances, whereby expected uses of technology are purposefully detached and transformed within the sphere of the school. For instance, Nancy's efforts to redirect students who become overly engrossed in VR exemplify how enactments are given shape by a teacher who reconfigures how VR engagement can unfold. Such enactments suspend linearity and counter foreseeable patterns (cf. Bacalja, 2024), and form a constitutive part of engaging with technology in classrooms. Our case illuminates that when technological developments unfold within the school, the expectations of digital technologies are ultimately rearranged and re-negotiated – and thus differentially enacted – in concrete school realities.

In this sense, sociomaterial arrangements and actions of school actors differentially enact digital technology in school education but also make engagement with technology possible in the first place, albeit within particular limits. Additionally, however, our vignettes show how throughout differential enactments, certain attachments (i.e. communizing, instancing, modulating, conditioning) stick, signifying who and what becomes of pedagogical concern. The four attachments identified in this paper can be understood as *pedagogical attachments* that offer a way to systematize how technologies give way to pedagogical relations in school practices. These emergent pedagogical attachments indicate ways of relating to each other and 'things' of concern in the classroom, while relegating others to the background, that make possible the generation and sustaining of educational practice itself (cf. Law, 1993). Ultimately, and particular for our case, we have explored how such pedagogical attachments not only emerge, but in turn give shape to forms of immersion (as objectual togetherness and as displacement), which indicate technological ways of being and the world-making capacity of technology in education. Immersion, in this sense, is characterized by multiplicity and alludes to affectual states that are not limited to an individual wearing a VR headset. It rather signifies certain states of classroom activity with technology where distinct actions and things pedagogically matter and are engaged with, and others less so. Consequently, immersion both precedes and is variously made possible by the way technology is individually and collectively practiced (Mühlhoff & Schütz, 2019). It denotes a mode of being with technology that fosters a way of paying attention to matters of pedagogical concern in the classroom, and is hence (part of) that which momentarily – that is, insofar as attachments are sustained – makes possible new ways of acting and thinking in education (cf. Woodward, 2024). The concept of immersion thus holds particular significance when investigating how technology-related attachments emerge and what this implies for school education from a pedagogical perspective.

To this extent, immersion allows to further 'think with' attachments (cf. de Laet et al., 2021). It opens possibilities to articulate how ways of being with technology emerge through attachments and makes explicit the ambiguity and counter-intuitive aspects related to technology becoming part of school practices, while allowing for a deeper understanding of the pedagogical relations that emerge in relation digital technology. Hence, it is important for STS-based educational research to further develop immersion

as a way to closely attend to the implications of pedagogical attachments that are generated in relation to technologies in schools. To this extent, the concept of immersion (and pedagogical attachments) further extends attempts to provide a generative reading of educational practices affected by, for example, technologies of datafication and platformization. By exploring immersion in everyday practices, it is possible to articulate educational ways of being that are in the making in proximity to digital technologies. Attention then shifts towards exploring pedagogically meaningful forms of school practice that occur in relation to or precisely against these technologies, and imagining how these can be fostered in the future (cf. Zakharova & Jarke, 2022).

7. Concluding thoughts

The rise in popularity of VR, coupled with significant investments in the technology, has positioned it as a transformative tool within VET and school education more broadly. Proponents frame VR as a tool to bridge the gap between education and the job market by rendering 'real' workplace scenarios tangible within schools and immersing students in virtual environments. This paper has explored the ways VR is used in one school in Flanders to study how pedagogical attachments emerge and how these attachments, ultimately, give rise to forms of immersion with technology in the sphere of the school. Significantly, our analysis shows that while VR is often touted as a tool for individual immersive experiences, immersion is not an inherent quality of VR. Rather, it is a dynamic enactment that materializes differently depending on how attachments (and detachments) are fostered in classrooms and, thus, on how VR comes into being within specific practices (Scott & Orlikowski, 2014). Immersion in that sense alludes to ways of acting and thinking, and thus of being engaged in practice, that are made possible and actively sustained by various educational actors. Our main contribution herein lies in illuminating the pedagogical specificity of how technological immersion manifests in different forms within educational practice (cf. Lucia et al., 2024), and how it unfolds not despite of but precisely *because of* what is often called 'disruption' and 'noise' in schools. Conclusively, our paper shows how, beyond the differential ways technologies are enacted in school education and the work that is put into them to make them appear in specific ways (cf. Sørensen, 2007), pedagogical attachments emerge that are indicative of the world-making capacity of technologies in the classroom. We argue that future research needs to further explicate the pedagogical specificities of various educational technologies, rather than (only) having a general focus on how digital technology as such is always and necessarily differentially enacted in the classroom in the same way (cf. Latour, 2013).

Notes

1. For this reason, to avoid operationalizing VR as an empty signifier that encompasses every type of virtual environment, we only use 'VR' to indicate computer-generated virtual environments that can be engaged with through an HMD.
2. Personal information has been pseudonymized.
3. This research is part of an international research project called 'SMASCH' (<https://www.smasch.eu/en/>), which focuses both on exploring how digital technologies unfold in Flemish and German schools and on collaborating with schools on developing pedagogically meaningful practices and approaches concerning technology.

Acknowledgments

An earlier draft of this paper was discussed in a seminar of the research group ‘Digital Education and Schooling’ at the Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg. We would like to express our gratitude to the colleagues who took part in this seminar and for the valuable critical ideas and feedback they provided to develop this paper further. We are furthermore grateful to School Athena, and its principal, ICT coordinator, teachers, and students, who agreed to the fieldwork and for the many crucial insights they each have provided. This paper could not have been written without their ideas and engagement.

Approved by ethics committee

Sociaal Maatschappelijke Ethische Commissie [Social and Societal Ethics Committee] (SMEC). Approval number: G-2021–4217-R3(AMD)

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This work is funded by dtec.bw – Digitalization and Technology Research Center of the Bundeswehr. dtec.bw is funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU.

Notes on contributors

Toon Tierens is a postdoctoral researcher at the Zurich University of Teacher Education. His main research interests include school education in the digital condition, school development, Science and Technology Studies, and qualitative research methodologies.

Mathias Decuyper is professor in education with a focus on school development and governance at the Zurich University of Teacher Education (Switzerland) and is equally affiliated to KU Leuven (Belgium). His main interests are situated at the digitization, datafication and platformization of education; and how these evolutions enact distinct forms of education policy, governance, and practice.

Sigrid Hartong is professor in sociology with a focus on the transformation of governance in education and society at the Helmut Schmidt University (HSU), Hamburg (Germany). Her main scholarly interests include global–local reform mobilities, from both single-case and international comparative perspectives, as well as the growing datafication and digitalization of education policy, governance and practice.

Samira Alirezabeigi is a voluntary researcher at the research group Education, Culture and Society, KU Leuven (Belgium). Her research interests include digitization of education, qualitative research methodologies, sociomaterial approaches, and philosophy of education.

ORCID

Toon Tierens <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-3994-9710>

Mathias Decuyper <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-0983-738X>

Sigrid Hartong <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8618-4837>

Samira Alirezabeigi <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-2783-4438>

References

- Aberton, H. (2012). Material enactments of identities and learning in everyday community practices: Implications for pedagogy. *Pedagogy, Culture & Society*, 20(1), 113–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681366.2012.649418>
- Adams, C. A., & Thompson, T. L. (2011). Interviewing objects: Including educational technologies as qualitative research participants. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*, 24(6), 733–750. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2010.529849>
- Bacalja, A. (2024). Postdigital game-based learning: Complexity, continuity, and contingency. *Postdigital Science & Education*, 7(2), 523–541. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-024-00506-z>
- Bayne, S. (2015). What's the matter with 'technology-enhanced learning'? *Learning, Media and Technology*, 40(1), 5–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2014.915851>
- Bloom-Christen, A., & Grunow, H. (2022). What's (in) a vignette? History, functions, and development of an elusive ethnographic sub-genre. *Ethnos*, 89(5), 786–804. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00141844.2022.2052927>
- Brightenti, A. (2007). Visibility: A category for the social sciences. *Current Sociology*, 55(3), 323–342. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011392107076079>
- Candea, M. (2010). “I fell in love with Carlos the meerkat”: Engagement and detachment in human-animal relations. *American Ethnologist*, 37(2), 241–258. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1548-1425.2010.01253.x>
- Carlsson, S., & Willermark, S. (2023). Teaching here and now but for the future: Vocational teachers' perspective on teaching in flux. *Vocations & Learning*, 16(3), 443–457. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12186-023-09324-z>
- Chalmers, D. (2022). *Reality+*. *Virtual worlds and the problems of philosophy*. Penguin Random House.
- Clarke, A. C. (1956). *The city and the stars*. Frederick Muller Ltd.
- Cone, L. (2024). Subscribing school: Digital platforms, affective attachments, and cruel optimism in a Danish public primary school. *Critical Studies in Education*, 65(3), 294–311. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17508487.2023.2269425>
- Dahalan, F., Alias, N., & Shaharom, M. S. N. (2024). Gamification and game based learning for vocational education and training: A systematic literature review. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29(2), 1279–1317. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11548-w>
- Davidson, J., & Paulsen, L. (2024). Postdigital virtual reality. In P. Jandrić (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of postdigital science and education*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-35469-4_73-1
- Decuyper, M., & Simons, M. (2019). Continuing attachments in academic work in neoliberal times: On the academic mode of existence. *Critical Studies in Education*, 60(2), 226–244. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17508487.2016.1240095>
- de Laet, M., Driessen, A., & Vogel, E. (2021). Thinking with attachments: Appreciating a generative analytic. *Social Studies of Science*, 51(6), 799–819. <https://doi.org/10.1177/03063127211048804>
- de Vasconcelos, G. N. (2021). *Atmospheres of immersion: Designing and experiencing in architecture and virtual reality* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation] Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais. <https://repositorio.ufmg.br/handle/1843/38860>
- Enochsson, A.-B., Kilbrink, N., Andersén, A., & Ådefors, A. (2020). Connecting school and workplace with digital technology: Teachers' experiences of gaps that can be bridged. *Nordic Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 10(1), Article 1. 43–64. <https://doi.org/10.3384/njvet.2242-458X.2010143>
- European Commission. (2023, August 31). *Vocational education and training initiatives-European Education Area*. Vocational Education and Training Initiatives. Retrieved from <https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/vocational-education-and-training/about-vocational-education-and-training>
- Flemish Government. (2024). *Extended reality in de klas (Extended reality in the classroom)*. Retrieved from <https://Onderwijs.Vlaanderen.Be/Nl/Onderwijspersoneel/van-Basis-Tot-Volwassenenonderwijs/Lespraktijk/Extended-Reality-in-de-Klas> .

- Flemish Government. (2019). Beleidsprioriteiten onderwijs en vorming: Bijdrage van het beleidsdomein onderwijs en vorming aan het regeerakkoord (Policy priorities education and training: Contribution of the policy domain education and training to the coalition agreement). Retrieved from <https://www.vlaanderen.be/publicaties/beleidsprioriteiten-onderwijs-en-vorming-bijdrage-van-het-beleidsdomein-onderwijs-en-vorming-aan-het-regeerakkoord-2019-2024>
- Forsler, I. (2024). Virtual reality in education and the co-construction of immediacy. *Postdigital Science & Education*, 7(2), 502–522. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-024-00492-2>
- Fransson, G., Holmberg, J., & Westelius, C. (2020). The challenges of using head mounted virtual reality in K-12 schools from a teacher perspective. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(4), 3383–3404. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10119-1>
- Freitag, F., Molter, C., Mücke, L. K., Rapp, H., Schlarb, D. B., Sommerlad, E., Spahr, C., & Zerhoch, D. (2020). Immersivity: An interdisciplinary approach to spaces of immersion. *Ambiances Environnement Sensible, Architecture et Espace Urbain*. <https://doi.org/10.4000/ambiances.3233>
- Garforth, L. (2012). In/visibilities of research: Seeing and knowing in STS. *Science, Technology, and Human Values*, 37(2), 264–285. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243911409248>
- Gomart, E. (2002). Towards generous constraint: Freedom and coercion in a French addiction treatment. *Sociology of Health and Illness*, 24(5), 517–549. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9566.00307>
- Gomart, E., & Hennion, A. (1999). A sociology of attachment: Music amateurs, drug users. *Sociological Review*, 47(1_suppl), 220–247. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-954X.1999.tb03490.x>
- González López, A. E., & Büchner, F. (2024). Edtech in a broken world: Breaking and repairing in Argentinian and German schools. *Postdigital Science & Education*, 6(4), 1261–1286. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-024-00490-4>
- Hangartner, J., Hürzeler, D., & Aebli, N. (2024). Everyday approaches to platform-mediated personalized learning in secondary schools. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2024.2367051>
- Harley, D. (2024). “This would be sweet in VR”: On the discursive newness of virtual reality. *New Media and Society*, 26(4), 2151–2167. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448221084655>
- Hennion, A. (2017). Attachments, you say? . . . How a concept collectively emerges in one research group. *Journal of Cultural Economy*, 10(1), 112–121. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17530350.2016.1260629>
- Jandrić, P., MacKenzie, A., & Knox, J. (2023). Postdigital research: Genealogies, challenges, and future perspectives. In P. Jandrić, A. MacKenzie, & J. Knox (Eds.), *Postdigital research: Genealogies, challenges, and future perspectives* (pp. 3–10). Springer Nature Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-31299-1>
- Jongbloed, J., Chaker, R., & Lavoué, E. (2024). Immersive procedural training in virtual reality: A systematic literature review. *Computers and Education*, 221, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2024.105124>
- Jossberger, H., Brand-Gruwel, S., van de Wiel, M. W. J., & Boshuizen, H. P. A. (2015). Teachers’ perceptions of teaching in workplace simulations in vocational education. *Vocations & Learning*, 8(3), 287–318. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12186-015-9137-0>
- Latour, B. (1992). *Aramis ou l’amour des techniques*. La Découverte.
- Latour, B. (1999). Fractures/fractures: From the concept of network to the concept of attachment. *Res*, 36(Autumn), 20–31. <https://doi.org/10.1086/RESv36n1ms20167474>
- Latour, B. (2005a). From realpolitik to dingpolitik. Or how to make things public. In B. Latour & P. Weibel (Eds.), *Making things public: Atmospheres of democracy* (pp. 14–41). The MIT Press. <http://www.bruno-latour.fr/sites/default/files/96-DINGPOLITIK-GB.pdf>
- Latour, B. (2005b). *Reassembling the social: An introduction to actor-network-theory*. Oxford University Press.
- Latour, B. (2013). *An inquiry into modes of existence: An anthropology of the moderns*. Harvard University Press.
- Law, J. (1993). *Organising modernity: Social ordering and social theory*. Wiley-Blackwell.

- Law, J., & Singleton, V. (2000). Performing technology's stories: On social constructivism, performance, and performativity. *Technology and Culture*, 41(4), 765–775. <https://doi.org/10.1353/tech.2000.0167>
- Lege, R., & Bonner, E. (2020). Virtual reality in education: The promise, progress, and challenge. *The JALT CALL Journal*, 16(3), 167–180. <https://doi.org/10.29140/jaltcall.v16n3.388>
- Light, B., Burgess, J., & Duguay, S. (2018). The walkthrough method: An approach to the study of apps. *New Media and Society*, 20(3), 881–900. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444816675438>
- Lucia, B., Vetter, M. A., & Solberg, D. A. (2024). “I feel like I’m in a box”: Contrasting virtual reality “imaginaries” in the context of academic innovation labs. *Technical Communication Quarterly*, 33(4), 429–444. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10572252.2023.2245442>
- Lury, C., & Wakeford, N. (2012). Introduction: A perpetual inventory. In C. Lury & N. Wakeford (Eds.), *Inventive methods: The happening of the social* (pp. 1–24). Routledge.
- Macgilchrist, F. (2021). Theories of postdigital heterogeneity: Implications for research on education and datafication. *Postdigital Science & Education*, 3(3), 660–667. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-021-00232-w>
- Macgilchrist, F. (2025). Educational ethnography in an age of technoculture: Exploring noise and glitch instead of fetishising the new. In J. Budde, A. Wischmann, G. Rißler, & M. Meier-Sternberg (Eds.), *Novelty, innovation and transformation in educational ethnographic research* (pp. 16–28). Routledge.
- Madary, M., & Metzinger, T. K. (2016). Real virtuality: A code of ethical conduct. Recommendations for good scientific practice and the consumers of VR-Technology. *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frobt.2016.00003>
- Mills, K. A., & Brown, A. (2022). Immersive virtual reality (VR) for digital media making: Transmediation is key. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 47(2), 179–200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2021.1952428>
- Mol, A. (2010). Actor-network theory: Sensitive terms and enduring tensions. *Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie Und Sozialpsychologie*, 50(1), 253–269.
- Mörtsell, S. (2024). Lesson enactments: Maintenance in everyday educational practice. *Postdigital Science & Education*, 6(2), 595–609. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42438-023-00401-z>
- Mühlhoff, R., & Schütz, T. (2019). Immersion, immersive power. In J. Slaby & C. von Scheve (Eds.), *Affective societies: Key concepts* (pp. 231–240). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351039260>
- OneBonsai. (2024). *Eerste hulp training in VR*. OneBonsai. Retrieved from <https://onebonsai.com/nl/vr-training/ehbo-training/>
- Paulsen, L., Dau, S., & Davidsen, J. (2024). Designing for collaborative learning in immersive virtual reality: A systematic literature review. *Virtual Reality*, 28(1), 63. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-024-00975-4>
- Pink, S., Ruckenstein, M., Berg, M., & Lupton, D. (2022). Everyday automation: Setting a research agenda. In S. Pink, M. Berg, D. Lupton, & M. Ruckenstein (Eds.), *Everyday automation: Experiencing and anticipating emerging technologies* (pp. 1–19). Routledge.
- Rose, M. (2018). The immersive turn: Hype and hope in the emergence of virtual reality as a nonfiction platform. *Studies in Documentary Film*, 12(2), 132–149. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17503280.2018.1496055>
- Scott, S. V., & Orlikowski, W. J. (2014). Entanglements in practice: Performing anonymity through social media. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(3), 873–894. <https://doi.org/10.25300/MISQ/2014/38.3.11>
- Simeone, A. L., Cools, R., Depuydt, S., Gomes, J. M., Goris, P., Grocott, J., Esteves, A., & Gerling, K. (2022). Immersive speculative enactments: Bringing future scenarios and technology to life using virtual reality. *Proceedings of the 2022 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '22)* (pp. 1–20). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491102.3517492>
- Sims, C. (2017). *Disruptive fixation: School reform and the pitfalls of techno-idealism*. Princeton University Press.
- Sørensen, E. (2007). The time of materiality. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung/Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-8.1.207>

- Spilski, J., Giehl, C., Schlittmeier, S., Lachmann, T., Exner, J.-P., Makhkamova, A., Werth, D., Schmidt, M., & Pietschmann, M. (2019). Potential of VR in the Vocational Education and Training of Craftsmen. *Proceedings of the 19th International Conference on Construction Applications of Virtual Reality (CONVR 2019)*, Bangkok, Thailand.
- Stender, B., Paehr, J., & Jambor, T. N. (2021). Using AR/VR for technical subjects in vocational training -. Of Substantial Benefit or Just Another Technical Gimmick? *2021 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)*, Vienna, Austria (pp. 557–561). <https://doi.org/10.1109/EDUCON46332.2021.9453928>
- St. Pierre, E. A. (2013). The appearance of data. *Cultural Studies ↔ Critical Methodologies*, 13(4), 223–227. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1532708613487862>
- Suchman, L. (2016). Configuring the other: Sensing war through immersive simulation. *Catalyst: Feminism, Theory, Technoscience*, 2(1), Article 1. 1–36. <https://doi.org/10.28968/cft.v2i1.28827>
- Sutherland, I. E. (1968). A head-mounted three dimensional display. *Proceedings of the December 9-11, 1968, Fall Joint Computer Conference, Part I*, San Francisco, California, USA (pp. 757–764). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1476589.1476686>
- Tanghe, E. (2023, July 3). *Preventie en veiligheid oudere zorgvrager: 360°-tour*. KlasCement. <https://www.klascement.net/oefeningen/169067/preventie-en-veiligheid-oudere-zorgvrager-360tour/>
- Taussig, M. (2011). *I swear I saw this: Drawings in fieldwork notebooks, namely my own*. University of Chicago Press.
- Turkle, S. (2017). *Alone together: Why we expect more from technology and less from each other*. Basic Books.
- Williamson, B. (2018). Silicon startup schools: Technocracy, algorithmic imaginaries and venture philanthropy in corporate education reform. *Critical Studies in Education*, 59(2), 218–236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17508487.2016.1186710>
- Woodward, N. (2024). John Cage and the aesthetic pedagogy of chance & silence. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 56(6), 547–556. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2023.2261618>
- Woolgar, S. (2002). Five rules of virtuality. In S. Woolgar (Ed.), *Virtual society? Technology, cyberbole, reality* (pp. 1–22). Oxford University Press.
- Zakharova, I., & Jarke, J. (2022). Educational technologies as matters of care. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 47(1), 95–108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2021.2018605>